

Statistical analyses

Linear model associated with data presented in Figure 5

Linear mixed model fit by REML. t-tests use Satterthwaite's method
['lmerModLmerTest']

Formula: CNV ~ treatment + (1 | generation) + (1 | replicate)

Data: ddpcr_pools_all_b

REML criterion at convergence: 19.1

Scaled residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-1.9180	-0.5189	0.1318	0.4273	2.2064

Random effects:

Groups	Name	Variance	Std.Dev.
generation	(Intercept)	0.07216	0.2686
replicate	(Intercept)	0.00000	0.0000
Residual		0.08117	0.2849

Number of obs: 23, groups: generation, 6; replicate, 2

Fixed effects:

	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	2.7501	0.1371	7.1572	20.063	1.49e-07 ***
treatmentsel	0.3559	0.1195	16.0983	2.978	0.00882 **

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Correlation of Fixed Effects:

(Intr)

treatmentsel -0.413

optimizer (nloptwrap) convergence code: 0 (OK)

boundary (singular) fit: see help('isSingular')

Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method

	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	NumDF	DenDF	F value	Pr(>F)
treatment	0.72008	0.72008	1	16.098	8.8714	0.008823 **

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1